

Conclusions on the virtual thematic events (D2.5)

Energytran

Research infrastructures cooperation for energy transition between European and Latin American and the Caribbean countries.

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Annex: Results of the VTE Surveys

1. Introduction

This document summarizes the key takeaways from the Virtual Thematic Events (VTE) carried out in Energytran Project: "Exploring Innovative Technologies, Policies, and Practices," held on June 26th and 27th, 2024; "The social impact of the energy transition", held on October 17th and 18th, 2024 and "Towards an Environmentally Sustainable Energy Transition", held on 8th and 9th October 2025.

Event 1: Exploring Innovative Technologies, Policies, and Practices

The event focused on strengthening EU-Latin America cooperation in the energy transition, aiming to address one of the key goals of the Energytran project: promoting cooperation and the exchange of best practices between both regions. This collaborative approach seeks to leverage the expertise and resources of both regions to advance towards a sustainable energy future.

The event brought together experts from Europe and Latin America to engage in discussions centered around three main areas: technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, and successful practices in the transition towards a sustainable energy future. This multifaceted approach underscores the understanding that a successful energy transition requires a holistic perspective that goes beyond purely technical solutions.

The summary included in this document will highlight the technological and regulatory aspects discussed throughout the five panels of the event, while also touching upon the social and environmental impacts, as these dimensions are crucial for ensuring a just and equitable transition. The event served as a valuable platform for knowledge exchange, fostering collaboration opportunities, and contributing to a shared vision of a sustainable energy future for Europe and Latin America.

Event 2: The social impact of the energy transition

This event was focussed on one of the three main pillars of the Energytran project: the discussion of sociocultural and political aspects of the energy transition.

The event brought together experts from Iberoamerica with a collaborative approach that aims at promoting the cooperation of EU-Latin America experts in order to build a sustainable energy model and a just energy transition.

The summary included in this document will deep into the challenges that need to be addressed to make the energy transition socially just and politically feasible.

Event 3: Towards an Environmentally Sustainable Energy Transition

As the world advances from fossil fuels toward renewable energy, a new generation of innovative and impactful technologies is rapidly emerging. However, crucial discussions continue on how to implement renewable energy systems globally while ensuring that environmental, social, and economic dimensions are properly balanced.

The event addressed one of the project's three main pillars: the analysis of the environmental aspects of energy transition.

The meeting brought together distinguished experts from across EU and LAC countries to promote the exchange of knowledge, experiences, and best practices among researchers, policymakers, civil society, and the private sector in Europe, Latin America, and the Caribbean. Its objective was to foster collaboration in research and innovation while addressing shared environmental challenges linked to the transition toward sustainable energy systems.

The summary included in this document outlines the main insights and conclusions discussed during the event. In the annex is also included the main results of the surveys distributed at the end of each VTE.

2. Event 1: Exploring Innovative Technologies, Policies, and Practices

2.1. Event Description

The main goal of the event was to strengthen the cooperation between the European Union and Latin America in the area of energy transition. The event was structured around five thematic panels, each addressing a key aspect of the energy transition:

- **Panel 1: Knowledge Exchange in Scientific Cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean:** This panel, moderated by the Organization of Ibero-American States (OEI), focused on the importance of scientific cooperation to address common challenges in the energy transition, including the exchange of technological knowledge and the significance of research infrastructures.
- **Panel 2: Challenges and Opportunities in the Energy Sector:** Moderated by the National Center for High Technology (CeNAT) in Costa Rica, this panel analysed the current state of the energy sector in both Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean, as well as the perspectives and challenges of transitioning to clean energies. Topics discussed included alternative sources of clean energy, technological development, energy models, and opportunities in electric mobility, hydrogen, and wind farms.
- **Panel 3: Environmental and Social Impact of the Energy Transition:** Moderated by the National Council of Scientific and Technical Research of Argentina (CONICET) and the National University of San Martín (UNSAM), this panel examined the social and environmental implications of the energy transition, aiming to find answers for a just and equitable transition. Challenges for a just energy transition were discussed, including how the impacts manifest in local communities and what strategies governments and international cooperation can adopt to address them.
- **Panel 4: Emerging Technologies for Energy Sustainability:** This panel, moderated by the Pontifical Catholic University of Chile (PUC), focused on emerging technologies with the potential to drive energy sustainability, including green hydrogen and sustainable lithium extraction. Challenges and opportunities in the production of green hydrogen were discussed, as well as the need for suitable carriers for its transportation, the importance of collaboration and regulation, direct lithium extraction technology, and the diversification of value-added production in Latin America and the Caribbean.
- **Panel 5: Applications of Solar Thermal Energy:** This panel, moderated by CIEMAT-Solar Platform Almería (Spain), explored the various applications of solar thermal energy and its role in diversifying the energy matrix. Technological challenges and opportunities in solar thermal energy were discussed, including its use for electricity generation, process heat, and in rural areas. The role of solar thermal energy in energy policy was also analysed.
- **Panel 6: Conclusions and Closing:** The event concluded with a block dedicated to summarizing the discussions and drawing general conclusions. This block was divided into three parts: Synthesis and main conclusions of the panels (representatives from each panel presented a 9-minute summary of the main conclusions); general conclusions of the event (this section, with a duration of 22 minutes, included a debate among the members of the Energytran project, seeking a transversal perspective that integrated the different themes addressed); acknowledgments and closing (the event ended with a brief space for thanking the participants and organizers).

The participation was: 349 registrations. Attendees: 128 on the first day and 136 on the second day.

2.2. Panel 1: Knowledge Exchange in Scientific Cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean

Panel 1, titled "Knowledge Exchange in Scientific Cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean," focused on the importance of scientific cooperation to address shared challenges in the energy transition. This summary will cover the technological aspects discussed during the conversation.

Moderator

Paula Arranz: Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI)

Panellists

- Juan Vázquez Zamora: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)
- Sabina Guaylupo: Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology – FECYT (Spain)
- Karina Pombo: Observatory for Science, Technology and Society – OCTS (Argentina)

Main conclusions

Technological Aspects

Cooperation in research infrastructures emerged as a crucial element for knowledge exchange and the energy transition.

- **Importance of Collaboration:** Sabina Guaylupo, project manager of the EU-LAC RES INFRA PLUS project, highlighted the need for joint and complementary development of research infrastructures between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean. This development must consider the needs and capacities of both regions to ensure balanced and beneficial collaboration.
- **Benefits of Cooperation:** Building a joint strategy allows for adaptation to common standards, facilitates researcher training, expands access to facilities, services, and data, and promotes synergies and complementarities between the two regions. It was noted that the European Union has a more advanced collaboration framework in infrastructures through the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), while Latin America and the Caribbean still face challenges in collaboration due to a lack of knowledge about existing infrastructures and financial support.
- **Researcher Exchange:** The importance of facilitating the exchange of researchers between the two regions was emphasised. This exchange should not be limited to technical researchers but should also include infrastructure managers and directors to share management experiences and collaboration models. The importance of training highly skilled human capital in Latin America was highlighted to make the most of new technologies.
- **Access to Infrastructures:** The possibility for Latin American researchers to access European infrastructures was highlighted as a key factor in advancing the energy transition in the region. The need to expand access opportunities, which are often limited for researchers outside Europe, was mentioned. The Energytran project, as an example of collaboration, aims to facilitate knowledge and experience exchange between research infrastructures in both regions.

Concrete Examples

- **Energytran Project:** An example of scientific collaboration in the field of energy transition that seeks multidisciplinary solutions and promotes cooperation between European and Latin American institutions. The project includes mobility for researchers, technical assistance for indigenous and

rural communities in the use of green energy, and the development of an inventory of research infrastructures in both regions.

- **EU-LAC RES INFRA PLUS Project:** Aims to establish a sustainable bi-regional collaboration framework in the field of research infrastructures. This project works on identifying existing infrastructures, promoting collaborations, capacity building, and creating a joint roadmap. The importance of this project in creating a communication channel between the technical side and political decision-makers was highlighted.

Regulatory Aspects

Panel 1 mainly focused on the technological aspects of scientific cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean for the energy transition. Although the need for a regulatory framework to facilitate this cooperation was mentioned, the summary highlighted these points related to regulation:

- **Continuous Political Dialogue:** The need for ongoing political dialogue between the two regions to create a stable framework for collaboration was stressed.
- **Visibility and Communication:** The importance of giving greater visibility to existing research infrastructures and improving communication between the two regions was noted.
- **Identification of Needs:** The need to establish mechanisms for both regions to communicate their needs and objectives regarding cooperation in research infrastructures was raised.

2.3. Panel 2: Challenges and Opportunities in the Energy Sector

This panel discussed the challenges and opportunities of the energy sector in the context of the transition to clean energy, addressing issues such as decarbonization and the adoption of new consumption models.

Moderator

Allan Josué Campos Gallo: National Center for High Technology – CeNAT (Costa Rica)

Panellists

- Yendry Corrales Ureña: National Center for High Technology – CeNAT (Costa Rica)
- Ignacio Gil: Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science – INESC TEC (Portugal)
- Fernando Lizana: Expert in National Energy Distribution Networks and Renewable Energies (Costa Rica).
- Jose Henrique Querido Maia, Polytechnic Institute of Setubal (Portugal)

Main conclusions

Technological Aspects

The information presented during Panel 2 address various technological aspects related to the energy transition in Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean:

- **I Technological development and maturity:**
 - The difference in the **level of technological development between Europe and Latin America** is recognised. Europe has advanced in the implementation of clean energy, facing new challenges that become opportunities for development. Latin America, on the other

hand, has great potential but needs to mature its technological development processes, especially in the area of patents.

- **II. Infrastructure and energy models:**
 - The need to assess and modernise **energy generation and transmission infrastructures**, both nationally and regionally, is highlighted. Costa Rica is mentioned as a successful model for clean electricity generation, adaptable to other countries. The importance of regional integration to share strategies, resources, and technologies is emphasised.
 - The need for a **more flexible electricity system**, based on variable renewable energies, is identified. This involves decarbonising energy sources, adapting electrical systems at all levels, and understanding growth limits. Microgrids are mentioned as an option for energy management.
- **III. Energy storage:**
 - **Energy storage** is recognised as a critical challenge, especially given the volatility of renewable energies. Batteries are mentioned as an option, but more research and innovation are needed in this field.
- **IV. Specific technologies:**
 - **Green hydrogen:** Its potential in maritime transport and the decarbonisation of islands is discussed. It is noted that research and development funding in Europe increasingly considers green hydrogen as a key energy vector.
 - **Solar thermal energy:** The challenges and opportunities of concentrated (CSP) and non-concentrated solar thermal energy are presented.
 - **CSP:** The need to reduce costs, improve efficiency, and increase storage capacity is highlighted.
 - **Non-concentrated solar thermal energy:** The importance of developing low-cost, accessible systems for vulnerable and rural communities is emphasised. The need for more training for professionals in applying these technologies is mentioned.
 - **Demand management:** It is proposed as an important strategy to optimise energy use. Examples such as managing the charging of electric vehicles and cold production for refrigeration units are mentioned.
- **V. Role of academia:**
 - **Academia and research centres** are recognised as key players in knowledge transfer and the promotion of R&D&I in clean technologies. Their role in seeking sustainable solutions and building technology that responds to local needs is highlighted.

In summary, Panel 2 explored a variety of technological aspects related to the energy transition, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities this process presents for Europe and Latin America.

Regulatory Aspects

During the panel, several relevant points regarding regulation and the institutional framework for the energy transition were discussed.

- **Need for an appropriate regulatory framework:** The conclusions of Panel 2 mention the need for "an assessment and modernisation of energy generation and transmission infrastructures,"

which implies an adaptation of the regulatory framework to new technologies and energy models. During the debate, José Maya highlights the importance of regulation in the development of new technologies, specifically mentioning the need to "operationalise energy storage" and the creation of a regulatory framework for this type of technology.

- **Adaptation of market models:** Fernando Lizana, in his intervention, emphasises the importance of market models and their influence on the energy transition. A study by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) is mentioned, analysing the processes of market liberalisation since the 1990s and their impact on the adoption of clean energy. It is inferred that market models and regulation must be adapted to encourage investment in renewable energy, integrate new technologies, and allow new players to enter the energy sector.
- **Public policies and incentives:** The panel summary highlights the need for "integration between the EU and LAC to complement strategies, resources, and technologies," suggesting the importance of regulatory cooperation and the development of joint policies. The cases of Chile and Colombia are mentioned, where policies are being implemented to promote green hydrogen and attract investments. This underscores the importance of public policies and incentives for the development of new technologies and the energy transition.

In summary, the panel discussion offers relevant information on the importance of regulation, market models, and public policies in the energy transition. It can be concluded that the adaptation of the regulatory framework, the creation of appropriate incentives, and international cooperation are crucial elements for the success of the transition to a more sustainable energy model.

2.4. Panel 3: Environmental and Social Impact of the Energy Transition

This panel focused on the analysis of the social and environmental impact of the energy transition, seeking to identify strategies to mitigate negative impacts.

Moderator

Martín Obaya: National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET); School of Economics and Business at the National University of San Martín, (Argentina).

Panellists

- Carlos Monge Salgado: Publish What You Pay Coalition (PWYP) and Centre for Studies and Development Promotion (Peru).
- Melisa Escosteguy: Non-Conventional Energy Research Institute (INENCO), National Council of Scientific and Technical Research (CONICET), National University of Salta (Argentina).
- Eloy Sanz: Cabinet of the Presidency of the Government (Spain).

Main conclusions

Technological Aspects

Although there is no dedicated section on technological aspects within Panel 3, the presentations and discussions do mention how the technologies used in the energy transition can have social and environmental implications.

- **Raw material extraction:** Carlos Monge, in his presentation, mentions the need to "negotiate the conditions for the exploitation of the necessary minerals (strategic, critical) for the transition." This involves considering the environmental and social impact of mining lithium, copper, cobalt, and

others necessary for the manufacture of clean technologies such as solar panels, batteries, and wind turbines.

- **Territories and local communities:** Melisa Escosteguy focuses on the impacts of lithium mining in Argentina. While she does not delve into specific technological aspects, her analysis highlights the need to assess how the technologies used in extraction affect local communities and their ways of life.
- **Impact of energy production:** Although the main focus of the panel is not on energy generation technologies, it is acknowledged that the implementation of certain technologies, such as the construction of large hydroelectric dams or the expansion of large-scale solar energy, can generate significant environmental and social impacts, such as the displacement of communities or the alteration of ecosystems.
- **Need for an integrated approach:** The importance of considering technological aspects in the context of an integrated approach is emphasised, one that also includes social, environmental, economic, and governance dimensions.

In summary, Panel 3 highlights the importance of considering the social and environmental implications of the technologies used in the energy transition. It is acknowledged that the choice of technologies and their implementation must consider not only energy efficiency but also their impact on local communities, ecosystems, and social justice

Regulatory Aspects

The presentations and discussions within Panel 3 do provide relevant information on how regulation and the institutional framework play a crucial role in achieving a just and sustainable energy transition.

- **Regulation for a just transition:** Carlos Monge, in his presentation, highlights the importance of a regulatory framework that promotes a just energy transition. This involves:
 - **Regulation of extractive activities:** Monge stresses the need to "negotiate the conditions for mineral exploitation," which implies establishing clear and strict regulations for mining, ensuring respect for the rights of local communities and environmental protection.
 - **Citizen participation:** The importance of "free, prior, and informed consultation" in energy projects is mentioned, which implies the existence of a regulatory framework that guarantees citizen participation in decision-making processes.
 - **Equitable distribution of benefits:** According to Monge, a just energy transition must also ensure that the benefits are distributed equitably, which may require regulations for the distribution of tax revenues from energy activities.
- **Regulation for environmental protection:** Throughout the panel, the importance of "environmental standards and instruments" in the development of energy projects is mentioned. While specific regulations are not detailed, the need for a solid regulatory framework that guarantees environmental impact assessments, mitigation of negative impacts, and biodiversity conservation is inferred.
- **Technical assistance in regulatory matters:** Carlos Monge suggests that Europe can provide technical assistance to Latin America to "design and implement regulatory reforms and protocols" in environmental and citizen participation matters. This underscores the importance of international cooperation in strengthening regulatory capacities in developing countries.

In summary, Panel 3 highlights the crucial importance of a solid and just regulatory framework for a sustainable energy transition. The need for clear regulations on resource extraction, citizen participation, environmental protection, and equitable distribution of benefits is inferred. International cooperation is also considered an important factor in strengthening regulatory capacities and promoting a globally responsible energy transition.

2.5. Panel 4: Emerging Technologies for Energy Sustainability

This panel focused on the presentation and analysis of emerging technologies that can contribute to energy sustainability.

Moderator

Alvaro Videla: Pontifical Catholic University of Chile – PUC (Chile)– PUC (Chile).

Panellists

Felipe Huerta: Department of Chemical Engineering and Bioprocesses, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile (Chile).

Juan Carlos Fierro: Thematic Network of Value Chain Development of Strategic Minerals (México), National Technological Institute of Mexico.– TECNM (México).

Robert Szolak, Sustainable Synthesis Products (Germany), Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE (Germany).

Main conclusions

Technological Aspects

Panel 4: "Emerging Technologies for Energy Sustainability" focuses on the exploration of new technologies, particularly green hydrogen and sustainable lithium extraction, to drive the transition toward a more sustainable energy system.

- Green Hydrogen: Importance of developing new technologies:** The panel highlights the need to accelerate research and development of more efficient and cost-effective technologies for green hydrogen production. PEM electrolyzers are mentioned as a promising technology, though their costs remain high. ○ The need to develop solid oxide electrolyzers is emphasized, as they can utilize waste heat from industrial processes, improving efficiency and competitiveness.

Collaboration and regulation: The importance of collaboration between hydrogen producers and consumers is emphasized, as well as the need to establish clear regulations for the production, transportation, and use of this energy source.
- Sustainable Lithium Extraction: Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE) Technologies:** DLE technologies are presented as a more sustainable alternative to traditional evaporation techniques for extracting lithium from brines. The environmental advantages of DLE are highlighted, such as reduced water and energy consumption. It is recognized that DLE implementation is still limited, but these technologies are expected to minimize the environmental impacts of lithium production.

Challenges and opportunities in lithium production: Different lithium extraction methods are analysed, considering their advantages, disadvantages, and environmental impacts. Australia and Chile are mentioned as the main lithium producers, using pegmatites and brines, respectively. The need to invest in research and development to adapt extraction technologies to the specific characteristics of lithium deposits is acknowledged, with the aim of minimizing environmental impacts.
- Additional Technological Aspects: Electrification:** The panel also addresses the challenges and limitations of electrification as the sole solution for the energy transition. ○ It is recognized that not all industrial processes, long-distance transport, and heating can be fully electrified. The need to explore complementary alternatives to electrification, such as green hydrogen, is highlighted in order to achieve full decarbonization of the energy system.

In summary, Panel 4 focuses on technological advancements in green hydrogen and lithium extraction as key to energy sustainability. The panel analyses technological challenges, the importance of collaboration and regulation, and the need for an integrated approach combining different technologies to achieve a successful energy transition.

Regulatory Aspects

Although Panel 4 focuses on emerging technologies for energy sustainability, the panel does mention important regulatory aspects related to the development and implementation of technologies such as green hydrogen and lithium extraction.

- **Need for an adequate regulatory framework:** It is mentioned that the lack of a clear and specific regulatory framework for new technologies, such as green hydrogen production and Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE), may delay their development and large-scale implementation. This implies the need to establish standards and regulations that address: Technical standards for the production, storage, transportation, and use of green hydrogen. Regulation of water and waste management in lithium extraction, especially for DLE technologies. Incentives for investment in clean technologies and the creation of a market for green hydrogen.
- **Importance of international collaboration:** The importance of international cooperation in the development of clean technologies and the creation of a more sustainable global energy system is highlighted. This includes: Knowledge exchange and best practices in regulation and technological development. Cooperation in research and development projects for clean technologies. Establishment of trade agreements to facilitate the trade of green hydrogen and other renewable energy-related products.
- **Human capital development:** The panel mentions the need to train specialized human capital in new technologies for energy sustainability. This implies: Investing in education and training in areas such as green hydrogen production, energy storage system management, and sustainable lithium extraction. Creating professional and technical training programs to prepare the workforce for the new demands of the energy sector.

In summary, Panel 4 underscores the crucial importance of an adequate regulatory framework to drive the development and implementation of emerging technologies for energy sustainability. It recognizes the need to establish clear standards, promote international collaboration, and invest in the training of specialized human capital to fully harness the potential of these technologies

2.6. Panel 5: Applications of Solar Thermal Energy

This last panel addressed the applications of solar thermal energy, analyzing the technological challenges and opportunities in this field.

Moderator

Ricardo Sánchez Moreno: Energy, Environmental and Technological Research Centre – Solar Platform of Almeria (CIEMAT – PSA) (Spain).

Panellists

- Clotilde Noemi Sogari: National University of the Northeast (Argentina).
- Alejandro Luis Hernández: Non-Conventional Energy Research Institute (INENCO), National Council of Scientific and Technical Research (CONICET), National University of Salta, (Argentina).
- Manuel Blanco, Bluesolar Filters S.L. (Spain), SuVanguard Dynamics S.L. (Spain), German Aerospace Center – DLR (Germany).
- Xavier Lara, AELIUS Energies (Spain), SolStor Energy (USA).

Main conclusions

Technological Aspects

Panel 5, titled "Applications of Solar Thermal Energy," focuses on exploring the various applications of this technology for clean energy generation and its role in the energy transition. The presentations and discussions provide a wide range of information on key technical aspects of solar thermal energy.

- **Concentrated Solar Thermal Energy (CSP):**
 - I. **Central Tower Systems:** Central tower systems are described as a widely used CSP technology. These systems use heliostats (movable mirrors) to concentrate solar radiation onto a receiver located at the top of a tower. The heat generated in the receiver is used to heat a working fluid, which in turn drives a turbine to generate electricity.
 - II. **Challenges and Opportunities:** Challenges and opportunities in the development of CSP technology are identified, including:
 - a) **Efficiency Improvement:** The importance of research to improve the capture, concentration, and conversion efficiency of solar energy in CSP systems is mentioned.
 - b) **High-Temperature Receivers:** High-temperature receivers are highlighted as a promising research area, as they enable more efficient power cycles. Particle receivers and sodium receivers are mentioned as examples.
 - c) **Thermal Storage:** The thermal storage capability of CSP technology is emphasized as a significant advantage over other renewable energies. The need to expand the portfolio of storage materials and improve the reliability of existing systems is noted.
 - d) **Integration with Other Technologies:** The importance of integrating CSP with other technologies, such as photovoltaic, wind, and green hydrogen, is discussed to create more resilient and flexible energy systems.
 - e) **Digitalization:** The potential of digitalization, artificial intelligence, and drones to optimize the operation and maintenance of CSP plants, thereby reducing costs, is recognized.

- **Non-Concentrated Solar Thermal Energy:**
 - I. **Applications:** Various applications of non-concentrated solar thermal energy are presented, such as water heating for domestic and industrial use, space heating, agricultural product drying, and water distillation.
 - II. **Bioclimatic Buildings:** The role of non-concentrated solar thermal energy in the construction of bioclimatic buildings, which harness solar energy to reduce energy consumption and improve thermal comfort, is highlighted.
 - III. **Challenges and Opportunities:** Challenges and opportunities in the development of non-concentrated solar thermal energy are analysed, including:
 - a) **Cost Reduction:** The need to reduce the costs of solar thermal systems to make them more accessible to vulnerable communities is mentioned.
 - b) **Simplicity and Accessibility:** The importance of developing simple technologies, using affordable and readily available materials, is emphasized to facilitate their adoption in different contexts.
 - c) **Training and Education:** The necessity of training the population in the design, installation, and maintenance of solar thermal systems is underscored to ensure their proper functioning and durability.
 - d) **Adaptation to Context:** The importance of adapting technologies to climatic conditions and the specific needs of each region is noted.

In summary, Panel 5 provides a detailed view of the technological aspects of solar thermal energy, both concentrated and non-concentrated. It analyses the different technologies, their applications, challenges, and opportunities, highlighting their potential to contribute to the transition towards a more sustainable energy system.

Regulatory Aspects

The presentations and discussions within Panel 5 do address the importance of energy policy and mention several relevant regulatory aspects for the successful implementation of solar thermal energy.

- **Need for Supportive Energy Policies:** The importance of government energy policies promoting solar thermal energy is highlighted, recognizing its advantages for decarbonization and the creation of more resilient energy systems.
- **Incentives and Regulations:** Specific examples of policies that can drive the adoption of solar thermal energy are mentioned, such as:
 - **Tax Incentives and Grants:** To make solar thermal systems more economically accessible.
 - **Financing Programs:** To facilitate investment in solar thermal energy projects, especially in rural communities.
 - **Energy Efficiency Regulations:** That establish requirements for the use of renewable energies in buildings, thereby boosting the demand for solar thermal systems.
- **Creation of a Clear Regulatory Framework:** The need for a transparent regulatory framework that provides security to investors and promotes the development of the solar thermal energy supply chain is mentioned.

- **Local Content and Job Creation:** The importance of energy policies considering local content and job creation in the solar thermal energy industry is emphasized.

In summary, the importance of energy policies and an appropriate regulatory framework for driving the implementation of solar thermal energy is recognized. Concrete examples of supportive policies, such as tax incentives and energy efficiency regulations, are mentioned as key to overcoming economic barriers and promoting the adoption of this clean technology.

2.7. Panel 6: Conclusions and Closing

Moderator

Jose Martín Martínez: EU-SOLARIS ERIC

Adrián Bonilla: National Technological Institute of Mexico.– TECNM (Mexico).

Panellists

- Paula Sanchez-Carretero: Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI).
- Allan Josué Campos Gallo: National Center for High Technology – CeNAT (Costa Rica).
- Emilio Santiago: Higher Council for Scientific Research – CSIC (Spain)
- Arturo Ignacio Morande Thompson: Pontifical Catholic University of Chile – PUC (Chile).
- Clotilde Noemi Sogari: National University of the Northeast – UNNE (Argentina).

Main conclusions

Block 1: Conclusions and Closing: Synthesis and Key Conclusions of the Panels

Block 1 of the section "Conclusions and Closing" of the event "Technology and Energy Transition: Strengthening Europe-Latin America Cooperation in the Energy Transition" was dedicated to presenting the syntheses and main conclusions of the five panels that comprised the event. Below is a summary of each panel:

Panel 1: Knowledge Exchange in Scientific Cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean

- **Key Conclusions:**
 - Scientific cooperation is essential for generating and transferring knowledge and technologies in the field of energy transition, regardless of the level of development of the countries.
 - The energy transition is not just an ecological crisis but a systemic crisis that requires cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.
 - Collaboration among different actors, including policymakers, civil society, the private sector, and academia, is fundamental for the success of the energy transition.
 - The need to create cross-sectoral alliances involving all stakeholders in the quadruple helix (academia, public sector, private sector, and civil society) was highlighted.
- **Key Points:**
 - The RES INFRA II project, a scientific cooperation initiative between Europe and Latin America, was presented.

- The importance of scientific diplomacy for the energy transition was emphasized.
- The need to address gender gaps in green transition sectors was identified.

Panel 2: Challenges and Opportunities in the Energy Sector

- **Key Conclusions:**

- Europe has developed strategies for the energy transition, but the transformation presents technological, cultural, environmental, strategic, and social challenges.
- Latin America and the Caribbean have great potential in clean energies but face difficulties in transforming their energy matrix.
- A thorough analysis of each sector and region is required to determine the best alternatives for clean generation.
- Integration and complementarity between the European Union and Latin America are essential for a successful energy transition.
- Costa Rica, despite its success in renewable energy generation, faces social and economic challenges.

- **Key Points:**

- The current situation of the energy sector in the European Union and Latin America and the Caribbean was discussed.
- The challenges of decarbonization and raw material acquisition were analysed.
- Opportunities in electric mobility, hydrogen, wind farms, and marine generation were explored.
- The role of academia and research centers as drivers of R&D in clean technologies was highlighted.

Panel 3: Environmental and Social Impact of the Energy Transition

- **Key Conclusions:**

- The energy transition must be socially just and equitable, considering the impacts on local communities.
- Implementing strong public policies and a global justice approach is crucial for ensuring a successful transition.
- The participation of local communities in decision-making is fundamental to ensure the acceptance and success of renewable energy projects.
- Experiences in Latin America, especially regarding consultation rights and the implementation of prior, free, and informed consultation, can be valuable for Europe.

- **Key Points:**

- The social challenges of Latin America and the Caribbean in the context of the energy transition, such as poverty, inequality, and environmental degradation, were analysed.
- Examples of best practices in renewable energy implementation in Spain were presented, highlighting the importance of socioeconomic integration, participatory site selection, and compensatory measures.

- The case of lithium mining in Argentina was discussed, showing the challenges and tensions that can arise with local communities if social and environmental impacts are not adequately addressed.

Panel 4: Emerging Technologies for Energy Sustainability

- **Key Conclusions:**

- The development of emerging technologies, such as green hydrogen and sustainable lithium extraction, is crucial for energy sustainability.
- A systemic approach that considers environmental, social, economic, and governance aspects is required for a successful energy transition.
- Creating a robust observation system that provides reliable information on the different aspects of the energy transition is essential.

- **Key Points:**

- The challenges and opportunities of the emerging green hydrogen industry were discussed.
- The importance of sustainable lithium extraction for the energy transition was analysed.
- The need for an appropriate regulatory framework to promote the development and implementation of these technologies was highlighted.

Panel 5: Applications of Solar Thermal Energy

- **Key Conclusions:**

- Solar thermal energy, both concentrated (CSP) and non-concentrated, has great potential to contribute to the energy transition.
- Support for research and development of CSP technology is required to improve its efficiency, reduce costs, and expand its implementation.
- Non-concentrated solar thermal energy offers solutions for water heating, space heating, agricultural product drying, and other applications, especially in rural areas.
- It is crucial to develop energy policies that encourage the adoption of solar thermal energy, including tax incentives, financing programs, and energy efficiency regulations.

- **Key Points:**

- The challenges and opportunities of CSP technology were presented, including improving efficiency, developing high-temperature receivers, thermal storage, and integration with other technologies.
- The applications of non-concentrated solar thermal energy and its importance for the construction of bioclimatic buildings were discussed.
- The need to reduce costs, simplify technology, provide training, and adapt solutions to local contexts for greater adoption of solar thermal energy was emphasized.

In summary, Block 1 of "Conclusions and Closing" provided a concise overview of the key points and main conclusions from each panel. The challenges and opportunities of the energy transition, the importance of international cooperation, the need for supportive energy policies, and the crucial role of technological innovation were highlighted.

Block 2: General conclusions of the event

Block 2 of the event, titled "General Conclusions of the Event," focused on an open debate among the partners of the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project. This debate, moderated by José (EU-Solaris ERIC) and Adrián Bonilla (National Technological Institute of Mexico), aimed to connect the themes addressed in the five panels and draw global conclusions about cooperation in the energy transition between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.

Below are the most relevant points from the debate:

- **Relevance of Local Context in the Energy Transition:** It was emphasized that the energy transition must adapt to local realities, considering the specific needs, resources, and challenges of each region. The case of Costa Rica was mentioned, which, despite its success in renewable energy generation, faces socio-economic challenges.
- **Importance of Cooperation and Knowledge Exchange:** The debate highlighted the need to strengthen cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean for a successful energy transition. The significance of sharing best practices, technologies, and governance models to drive innovation and develop solutions tailored to the needs of both regions was underscored.
- **Systemic and Inclusive Approach:** It was emphasized that the energy transition is not limited to technological aspects; it requires a systemic approach that considers social, economic, environmental, and governance factors. The importance of involving all relevant stakeholders in the process, including academia, the public sector, the private sector, and civil society, was highlighted.
- **Training and Human Capital:** The need to invest in training specialized human capital in clean technologies and energy policies was recognized. The importance of equipping workers, technicians, and professionals to drive innovation and implement renewable energy solutions was mentioned.
- **Regulation and Governance:** The importance of having clear, stable, and predictable regulatory frameworks that provide security to investors and promote investment in renewable energies was emphasized. The necessity of designing efficient market mechanisms and implementing public policies that encourage the adoption of clean technologies was discussed.
- **Importance of the Social Dimension:** The debate highlighted the need to approach the energy transition from a social justice perspective, ensuring that the benefits of the transformation reach all sectors of society. The necessity of considering impacts on local communities, especially in areas where raw materials for renewable energies are extracted, was mentioned.
- **The Role of Science and Technology:** The crucial role of science, technology, and innovation in finding solutions to the challenges of the energy transition was acknowledged. The importance of research and development of clean technologies, as well as creating robust information systems to monitor progress and make informed decisions, was emphasized.

In summary, Block 2 of the event "Technology and Energy Transition" provided a space for open and constructive dialogue where partners of the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project could share perspectives, identify challenges and opportunities, and outline general conclusions regarding cooperation in the energy transition between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean. The importance of a comprehensive, inclusive approach adapted to local realities for advancing towards a sustainable energy future was highlighted.

Block 3: Acknowledgments and closing

Block 3 of the "Technology and Energy Transition" event was dedicated to acknowledgments and the closing of the thematic virtual event.

Acknowledgments:

- **Participants and Attendees:** Thanks were extended to all participants of the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project for their commitment, effort, and contributions to the event. Special gratitude was expressed to the audience for their interest, active participation, and questions throughout the two days of the event.
- **Organizers and Sponsors:** The joint efforts of the Organization of Ibero-American States (OEI) and EU-Solaris ERIC in organizing the event were recognized, highlighting the cooperation and collaborative effort that made the event successful. The European Union was thanked for its financial support of the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project.
- **Project Partners:** A special mention was made of each of the partners in the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project: LifeWach ERIC, UNNE, IPS, PUC, CENAT, UNSAM, INESC TEC, OEI, CSIC and EU-Solaris ERIC. The value of cooperation among these institutions in achieving the project's objectives was highlighted.

Closing:

- **Final Message:** The importance of cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean in advancing towards a just, equitable, and sustainable energy transition was emphasized. The thematic virtual event was noted as a successful example of collaboration, knowledge exchange, and networking among project partners and the scientific community.
- **Upcoming Events:** The audience was invited to participate in upcoming events of the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project, mentioning that the next event will focus on the social impact of the energy transition and will be coordinated by CSIC (Spain).
- **Farewell:** The event concluded with a message of optimism and hope, highlighting the importance of international cooperation in addressing the challenges of the energy transition and building a sustainable energy future for all.

Block 3 of the event served to express gratitude to all those involved in the thematic virtual event and to reaffirm the commitment of the EULAC ENERGYTRAN project to cooperation and knowledge exchange for a successful energy transition. The community was invited to continue participating in the project's activities and to contribute to the dialogue and collaboration between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.

3. Event 2: The Social Impact of Energy Transition in Ibero-America

3.1. Event Description

The event explored in depth the social challenges and therefore the cultural and political dimension of the Energy Transition. Today, although we have the substantial technologies to decarbonise the energy model, we lack the impetus and social consensus to do so at the appropriate speed. To achieve this, we need to establish the social framework in which the vast majority of the population feels that the energy transition is a gain, for which it is essential to guarantee social justice in its planning and development. The event's panels have developed key aspects of the different dimensions that this just energy transition must incorporate.

Panel 1. The social dimension of the Energy Transition. The first panel serves to introduce the social dimension of the energy transition in a panoramic way, emphasising why this is an essential variable to understand the complexity of the transition challenges.

Panel 2. Energy Transition and Territorial Justice in Iberoamérica. This panel focuses on underlining how territorial justice is a key component in ensuring that the energy transition can be seen and perceived as socially just.

Panel 3. Energy Transition and Gender Equality. This panel explores the nexus between energy and gender and the requirements for the energy transition to address current gender inequalities in order to mitigate them and ensure that women are included in the process.

Panel 4. Industrial policy and Energy Transition in Iberoamérica. This panel is dedicated to discussing how the energy transition can be the matrix of industrial policies that allow the nations of the Ibero-American space to redefine their productive model and their scheme of insertion in the global economy.

Panel 5. Public policies and Energy Transition in Iberoamérica. This panel is focused on analysing how public policies can help or hinder the successful development of a just energy transition.

Panel 6. Open Science and Energy Transition. The last panel explores the role that open science, as a collaborative and transparent research framework, plays in the energy transition and how it can contribute to an effective, just and democratic energy transition.

Conclusions: the event concluded with a block dedicated to summarizing the discussions and drawing general conclusions.

Participation:

The number of registrations was 341. The number of attendees was 82 on the first day and 89 on the second day.

3.2. Panel 1: The social dimension of Energy Transition

This is a propaedeutic panel reflecting on the social, cultural and political dimensions that condition the energy transition.

Moderator

César Rendueles: Higher Council for Scientific Research - CSIC (Spain).

Panellists

- Paula Peyloubet: Federal Network "Co-construir habitacion" (Argentina)
- Emilio Santiago: Higher Council for Scientific Research - CSIC (Spain).
- Paulo Magalhães: Centro Commun das Humanidades (Portugal)

Main conclusions

This introductory panel highlighted how political and social conflicts related to energy transition are expressed at different scales that can come into conflict.

Paula Peyloubet's presentation focused on the local scale, showing a type of environmental transition policies that involve dense social relations and that have very positive aspects in terms of labour and culture and that maintain complex relations with public-state intervention and with bureaucratic rationality. Relationships sometimes of tension, of conflict, but also of power and feedback.

Emilio Santiago's presentation addressed questions related to governance, not only in terms of how to construct technically viable public policies, but also by showing the social consensuses necessary to promote a just eco-social transition that manages to transform common sense and generate what Gramsci called a historical bloc. This point highlights issues that move on a different scale to the local one, which is the one on which some traditional environmentalism has operated, and which involves political and social commitments of a new order for environmental movements.

Paulo Magalhaes also reminded us of a basic question related to the scales of intervention, which is the question of the dilemma of the global commons. The ecosocial crisis is posed to us as a dilemma of the commons, not at the local scale as in the past, but as a dilemma of the commons at the global scale.

3.3. Panel 2: Territorial Justice and Energy Transition in the Ibero-American Space

It addresses the possibility of advancing the energy transition with territorial justice with a view that also encompasses the global space and the tensions that this provokes.

Moderator

Pedro Tomé, Higher Council for Scientific Research -CSIC (Spain).

Panellists

- Juan Requejo: Clave Technical Assistance (Spain)
- Carolina Palma: FIMA (Chile)
- Noemí Sogari, National University of the Northeast-UNNE (Argentina)

Main conclusions

In the second panel, fundamental concepts for thinking about energy transition with fairer characteristics emerged.

Renewable energies are allowing many technicians and political decision-makers to discover the notion of territory and, linked to this, that of local communities. If we want to move towards a just transition, it is necessary to take into account the needs and interests of these communities, because there is no justice without citizen participation and, in a broad sense, without democracy.

On the other hand, it was also shown how it is also essential to establish alliances between energy operators and the territories, and territorial planning systems that do not impose, but also do not hinder, the progress of this transition.

There will be no energy-environment transition if there is not also a social transition, a transformation of lifestyles, and putting care at the centre. We therefore need long-term energy policies that do not neglect social justice, sustainability and gender issues in the short term.

3.4. Panel 3: Gender equality and Energy Transition

It addresses the energy-gender nexus and the requirements of an energy transition that incorporates a gender perspective.

Moderator

Emilio Santiago: Higher Council for Scientific Research - CSIC (Spain).

Panellists

- Cristina de Benito, Higher Council for Scientific Research (Spain)
- Rosa Santero, Rey Juan Carlos University of Madrid (Spain)
- Giovanni Vecchio y Carolina Alejandra Rojas, , Institute of Urban and Territorial Studies, Pontifical Catholic University (Chile)

Main conclusions

There are several documented gender gaps in the social field of energy, which is a logical result of the fact that gender is a structural domination device in our societies. These gaps occur at different levels of the energy phenomenon, from the markedly feminine character of energy poverty to the strong occupational gender segregation in the labour market linked to the energy sectors, not to mention the specifically patriarchal dimension of violence suffered by women in communities involved in socio-energy conflicts.

Although in terms of discursive and normative frameworks the gender perspective is increasingly present, the real task now is to equip ourselves with the specific mechanisms and devices that will allow this gender approach to have real transformative effects.

There are interesting opportunities that have to do with the role of women in energy prosumer initiatives, actors who produce the very energy they consume through community-scale installations. And secondly, the greater willingness of women to engage in electromobility can make a gender-sensitive policy a tool to break the symbolic links between the private car and patriarchy.

We cannot ask energy transition to solve the problems of patriarchy, but neither can we admit that it does not take them into account, and this is a framework with which to orientate ourselves towards the future.

Gender-sensitive energy policies are essential not only for ethical and moral reasons, but also for efficiency reasons.

3.5. Panel 4: Industrial policy and Energy Transition in the Ibero-American Space

It delves into the debate on the return of industrial policy in the post-pandemic context and the importance of state action to enable the energy transition.

Moderator

Jaime Vindel, Higher Council for Scientific Research (Spain)

Panellists

- Martín Obaya, National Scientific and Technical Research Council-School of Economics and Business of the National University of San Martín (Argentina).
- Felipe Irarrázaval, School of Business and Center for Economic and Social Policies (CEAS)-Universidad Mayor. Center for Studies on Conflict and Social Cohesion (Chile)
- César Rendueles, Higher Council for Scientific Research (Spain)

Main conclusions

The contributions of the panel discussed the centrality of the state in the different aspects related to energy transition. It was shown how energy transition processes are conditioned by the competency frameworks of each of the nations and in this sense, it is fundamental to determine what the role of the state is in these undertakings, how the territorial distribution of competencies affects them, to what extent public companies can take charge of them, and whether or not public/private alliances are necessary and on what scale. All of this leads to the question of how the different exploitation models affect relations with the communities in the territories where these exploitations take place.

There was also a discussion on how to move forward with an energy transition from the centrality of the extraction of raw materials, as has historically occurred in Latin America, to production and the limits that are being encountered in this process. The objective would be to move from extraction to production and to do so under sustainable conditions. As conditioning factors, the productive and technological capacities, the capacity to capture income in alliances with the business world, and also the institutional capacities, the strength of the administrative apparatus, and the fiscal capacity of the different states to promote these policies, delving into horizons of social justice, were identified as conditioning factors.

Talking about the centrality of the state and the consensus on public intervention tells us nothing, however, about the nature of that intervention. It is important to see the different conflicting interests, the different actors involved: trade unions, employers, public authorities....

Finally, the key role of inherited cultural contexts in facilitating or hindering the energy transition was highlighted.

3.6. Panel 5: Public policies and Energy Transition in the Ibero-American Space

It makes the case that public policy is central to a just energy transition as it sets the regulatory framework that should ensure its success.

Moderator

Paula Arranz: Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI).

Panellists

- Erick Palomares, Transnational Institute (TNI) (México)
- Judith Carrera, Fair Transition Institute – Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge Ministry (Spain)
- Pedro Glazt, Former Advisor to the Ministry of the Environment (Chile)

Main conclusions

The panel emphasised the need to identify the regulatory challenges in the governance of energy resources because the adoption of technologies associated with the transition presents significant challenges at the policy and regulatory level. The existing legal frameworks in many Ibero-American countries are not fully adapted to manage the production, distribution and use of new clean energy sources, so it is necessary to update the regulations to facilitate the integration of these technologies, ensuring the safety, efficiency and sustainability of the process.

Knowledge was highlighted as a key factor in the energy transition. The transition depends not only on the adoption of new technologies but also on the ability to adapt innovations to local contexts. This implies understanding not only technical aspects but also the social and cultural characteristics of each region, making local knowledge an essential asset for designing public policies that are effective and equitable. Training and development of local skills and citizen participation are fundamental to ensure that energy technologies are used in a sustainable manner.

Finally, the importance of municipal and community integration was discussed: for the energy transition to be inclusive and successful, it is essential to involve municipal governments and communities in the planning and implementation of public policies. Decentralisation of energy governance can allow for better adaptation of policies to local needs and encourage citizen participation, which in turn facilitates better acceptance of these technologies.

3.7. Panel 6: Open Science and Energy Transition in the Ibero-American Space

In order to find innovative and effective solutions to achieve the goals of the energy transition, science plays a fundamental role. Open science enables efficient collaboration and the creation of research networks to help us achieve these goals.

Moderator

Luis Coelho, Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (Portugal).

Panellists

- Mark Urban: Clara Network
- Ximena Arizaga, Pontifical Catholic University (Chile)
- Judith Farré, Open Science Coordinator of the PTI-Digital Science of the Higher Council for Scientific Research (Spain)

Main conclusions

The academic community and the open science research community are key players in achieving the goals of the energy transition. Open science facilitates the exchange of information between different sectors such as academia, industry and government, promoting the creation of new solutions.

Open science provides a collaborative environment that not only contributes to innovation but also ensures that best practices and discoveries are disseminated, thus benefiting society as a whole.

Open science also makes scientific and technological advances more inclusive, involving civil society and local communities. It also, through transparency, builds public trust in energy transition initiatives, which is crucial for designing policies that promote a sustainable energy future.

There are more and more interconnected open science networks available to society to contribute to the energy transition pathway.

Therefore, it can be concluded that open science is a new paradigm that revolutionises scientific research and its social implication at a global level, contributing towards sustainable and people-centred development.

4. Event 3: Towards an Environmentally Sustainable Energy Transition

4.1. Event Description

The event explored the effects of alternative energy systems on the environment, the challenges associated to a sustainable energy transition, case studies showcasing solutions to mitigate environmental impacts, and policies and regulatory mechanisms in supporting a sustainable energy transition, structured across four thematic panels:

Panel 1: Challenges of a sustainable energy transition

This panel examined the complexities of achieving a truly sustainable energy future, including the evolving concept of sustainability, the interconnections between global development goals, and the social, political, and ethical dimensions of energy transitions. Discussions highlighted the need to balance resource demands, local and global interests, and environmental limits to ensure a just and effective transition.

Panel 2: Environmental impact of renewable energies

This panel explored the environmental implications of renewable energy deployment, including land use, ecosystem disturbance, and waste generation. Experts discussed sustainability assessments, life cycle analysis, critical raw material supply, and tools for evaluating both direct and indirect impacts to support evidence-based and environmentally responsible energy policies.

Panel 3: Solutions to environmental challenges in the energy transition

This panel explored practical solutions to promote an environmentally sustainable energy transition. Case studies highlighted approaches such as integrating sustainability into education and community projects, implementing sustainable lithium extraction technologies, and adopting circular bioeconomy practices. The discussions emphasized that local initiatives, when connected to broader strategies, can drive significant systemic change, demonstrating that a transition to a non-fossil fuel-based energy system is both feasible and environmentally responsible.

Panel 4: Policies and Regulations for the Green Energy Transition

This panel examined current policies and regulatory frameworks driving the green and sustainable energy transition, assessing their capacity to promote socioeconomic and environmental development across urban, rural, and remote contexts. It brought together perspectives from Latin America, Europe, and North America, enabling a comparative view of regional approaches. Discussions emphasized the need for regulatory systems that balance clean energy advancement with the sustainable use of natural resources. The importance of integrating ancestral and local knowledge into bioeconomy strategies was highlighted, as well as the crucial role of coherent policies to ensure that energy transitions are environmentally responsible, socially inclusive, and culturally respectful.

Participation:

The number of registrations was 298. The number of attendees was 80 on the first day and 75 on the second day.

4.2. Panel 1: Challenges of a sustainable energy transition

This panel brings together experts examining the complexities of achieving a truly sustainable energy future. Stéphan Barbe provides a historical perspective on sustainability, analysing its evolution and the interconnections between the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Diego Murguía explores justice and sustainability in critical mineral supply chains, using lithium as a case study to highlight tensions between local aspirations and European regulatory demands. Fernando Valladares emphasises the social and political dimensions of energy transitions, arguing that meeting human energy needs within planetary boundaries requires prioritising demand over market-driven production.

Moderators

Martín Obaya (Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas-Escuela de Economía y Negocios de la Universidad Nacional de San Martín, Argentina) - Vice-Director of the Research Center for Transformation (CENIT) at the School of Economics and Business, Universidad Nacional de San Martín (Argentina), and researcher at the National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET). His research focuses on the study of technological learning processes related to natural resources and the manufacturing industry. He is currently involved in research projects on governance processes and the development of productive capacities related to lithium.

Sandrina Moreira (Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal, Portugal) - Assistant professor at the Department of Economics and Management, School of Business Sciences, Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (DEG-ESCE-IPS) and researcher at BRU-IUL (Business Research Unit), ISCTE-IUL. Currently involved in two international research projects: (i) E³UDRES² (Learners & Educators at E3UDRES2 European University); (ii) EULAC for Energy Transition (more info below). PhD in Economics her research and teaching interests have focused on sustainable development | regional development and sustainability; circular economy | measurement and applications (including design thinking).

Panellists

Stéphan Barbe (University of Applied Sciences of Cologne, Germany) - Stéphan Barbe is an expert in sustainable chemical and biochemical engineering, with extensive experience bridging academic research and industrial innovation. His work focuses on developing environmentally responsible processes and products, integrating applied biology and engineering approaches. He is actively involved in European research and policy as a scientific expert for the European Commission.

Diego Murguía (CONICET - Universidad Nacional de San Martín, Argentina) - Diego Murguía is based in Buenos Aires and works as researcher at Argentina's National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET), the leading scientific institution in the country. He also works as fellow at the Research Center for Transformation (CENIT), belonging to the National University of San Martín, and is an associated researcher at the Institute for the Development of Sustainable Mining at the Catholic University of Salta. For the past two decades his research has been focused on value chain, governance and sustainability challenges around the metal mining sector with a focus on copper, gold and brine-based lithium.

Fernando Valladares (Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, España) Fernando Valladares holds a PhD in Biology and serves as a Senior Researcher at the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) and an Associate Professor at Rey Juan Carlos University in Madrid. He is a highly cited scientist with extensive research and publications on biodiversity, as well as the impacts of climate change and human activity on ecosystems. In 2021, he was awarded the Jaume I Prize in the category of Environmental Protection and the Environmental Communication Award from the BBVA Foundation. In 2023, he published *La Recivilización*, a book that encapsulates much of his scientific and philosophical thinking. In 2024, he received the Gold Medal of the Spanish Red Cross for his eco-social work and the Planet Earth Award from the Alliance of World Scientists for his outstanding efforts in communicating scientific knowledge on the climate crisis.

Main conclusions

Stéphan Barbe emphasized that sustainability is a dynamic and evolving concept, shaped by history, culture, and shifting societal values. Its meaning has transformed, from post-war priorities like peace and basic needs to contemporary focuses on justice, equality, and solidarity. While no universal definition exists, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) represent a global attempt to translate this complexity into measurable progress. Barbe underscored the interconnectedness of the SDGs, highlighting the need for integrated approaches that manage synergies and trade-offs across goals.

Diego Murguía addressed the environmental and social challenges of lithium extraction in South America amid rising global demand for the energy transition. He stressed that building a fair and sustainable EU–LAC lithium value chain requires balancing European supply security with Latin American sustainability and governance concerns, particularly regarding water use in fragile salt flat ecosystems. Murguía called for deeper cooperation, better regulation, and technological innovation, such as direct lithium extraction, to reduce environmental impacts and ensure social legitimacy through the inclusion of local communities.

Fernando Valladares argued that tackling the climate crisis demands a fundamental transformation of humanity's relationship with energy, how it is produced, consumed, and valued. Despite the urgency, fossil fuels still dominate the global mix, while their continued subsidies undermine climate goals. Renewables, though essential, also have environmental costs, requiring smarter use rather than expansion alone. Valladares called for more equitable energy distribution, efficiency, and reduced consumption, advocating for systemic changes (like electrification, circularity, and degrowth) to achieve well-being within planetary limits.

4.3. Panel 2: Environmental impact of renewable energies

Renewable energies are key to transitioning toward a more sustainable energy system. While their environmental impact is lower than that of non-renewables, challenges such as land use, ecosystem disturbance, and specific waste generation still require careful management. This panel brings together experts to examine these impacts. Diego Iribarren focuses on sustainability assessments and Life Cycle Analysis across European and Latin American contexts; José María Ponce Ortega addresses critical raw material availability, supply chain influences, and context-specific sustainability metrics; and Alejandro Caballeros explores open-source tools to evaluate direct and indirect impacts, supporting sustainable public policy decisions.

Moderator

Hilda Elizabeth Reynel Ávila (Tecnológico Nacional de México) - Hilda Elizabeth Reynel Ávila is a member of the National System of Researchers in Mexico, the Mexican Academy of Sciences, and the Mexican Academy of Catalysis. She conducts research in renewable energy and water treatment and is affiliated with the Aguascalientes Institute of Technology. She is also a member of several European consortia funded by the Organization of Ibero-American States and the European Union.

Panellists

Diego Iribarren (Instituto Madrileño de Estudios Avanzados de Energía, España) - Diego Iribarren has been working at the Systems Analysis Unit of IMDEA Energy (Madrid) since 2010, focusing his research on the sustainability of energy systems through life cycle approaches, energy modeling, and multi-criteria analysis. He has participated in national and international projects and currently coordinates the European HyPEF project on a sustainable hydrogen economy. He was coordinator of the Spanish Life Cycle Analysis Network (esLCA), has participated in international networks such as the IEA Hydrogen Technology Collaboration Programme and national networks like Red MENTES, and received the “Hydrogen Europe Research Young Scientist Award” in 2018.

José María Ponce Ortega (Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, México) - José María Ponce is a full professor at the Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, and a Level III member of the National System of Researchers of Mexico, the highest distinction. His research interests include water integration, energy planning and optimization, sustainable energy transition, the water-energy-food nexus, process integration, waste heat recovery, and sustainable production and consumption. He has led funded research projects and serves as Subject Editor of *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, Associate Editor of *Frontiers in Chemical Engineering*, and member of the editorial boards of several international prestigious journals.

Alejandro Caballeros Finkelstei (Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona, España) - Alejandro Caballeros is an economist with experience in research and public policy, specializing in environmental and energy sustainability. His work has focused on analyzing the sustainability of the energy transition, global environmental impacts, and energy security, participating in projects for institutions such as the Government of Spain, the Mexican Ministry of Energy, the World Bank, and the European Union. He has conducted research on displaced environmental impacts from international trade in the energy sector, energy vulnerability, and the criticality of strategic minerals to inform sustainability and energy policies.

Main conclusions

The panel concluded that comparing the importance of eco-indicators across regions and technologies is complex due to methodological differences and varying socio-economic contexts. Furthermore, the variability of impacts is influenced by differences in infrastructure, regulation, and economic development. The panel highlighted the importance of developing flexible methodological frameworks and open-source tools to evaluate direct and indirect impacts, including the extraction of critical raw materials, to support sustainable energy policies.

4.4. Panel 3: Solutions to environmental challenges in the energy transition

Complementing the perspectives shared in panels 1 and 2 about challenges related to environmentally sustainable energy transition, this panel explores concrete cases from Argentina, Chile, and Costa Rica as solutions to environmentally sustainable energy transition.

How can we address the effects of lithium mining on water resources and soil? How can we tackle the impact of wind farms on biodiversity or ensure the proper recycling of solar panels? How can we regulate the intensive land use and deforestation that may result from using biomass for energy production? From the analysis of specific cases, in this panel, we identified good practices and lessons that can be extrapolated to other geographic areas and thematic fields. Micro level must be closely connected to the macro level, therefore small initiatives can lead to major transformations. These initiatives demonstrate that a transition to a non-fossil fuel-based energy system is indeed possible and that this transition can be environmentally sustainable.

Moderator

Paula Sánchez Carretero (Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI) - Paula Sánchez-Carretero holds a degree in Economics and a postgraduate qualification in Sustainable Development and Climate Change, with expertise in Public Policy Evaluation and Innovation for Social and Environmental Transformation. With over 20 years of professional experience, she has specialized in evaluating public policies and cooperation projects related to sustainable development in Latin America and the Caribbean. She has also worked as a trainer and led numerous projects, studies, and evaluations for universities, companies, international organizations, and NGOs. Currently, she serves as Project Coordinator for Science at the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI) and as Coordinator of the EnergyTran project, while also acting as an external evaluator for cooperation initiatives and an observer in international missions.

Panellists

Edgardo Chapur (Universidad Nacional del Chaco Austral, Argentina) - Edgardo is an Industrial Engineer with a Master's in Business Administration and a specialization in Occupational Health and Safety. He currently serves as Director of the Environmental Institute at the National University of the Austral Chaco (UNCAUS) in Argentina, where he also teaches courses in engineering, marketing, and automation. With over 25 years of experience in telecommunications and academia, he has dedicated his career to promoting sustainability, renewable energy, and technological innovation in education. Under his leadership, UNCAUS has implemented impactful community projects such as the 60 kW Solar Eco-Parking, composting initiatives, and environmental education programs.

In his presentation, "*UNCAUS Sustentable: Educating by Example to Care for the Planet*," he highlighted how the university integrates sustainability into daily practice, combining clean energy generation with student learning and civic engagement. Emphasizing coherence between thought, speech, and action, he advocated that sustainability must be demonstrated—not just taught—and that “educating by example” is the most effective way to foster environmental values and social responsibility in future generations.

Álvaro Videla (Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile) - He holds a Ph.D. from the University of Utah, a Master of Science also from the University of Utah, and a degree in Industrial Civil Engineering from the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile (UC). He is an Associate Professor in the Department of Mining Engineering at UC and Director of the UC Energy Center. His research areas include energy consumption and process optimization in mining, technology analysis and opportunities in mining, critical

materials for the energy transition, energy storage using molten salts, lithium batteries, process optimization, and energy efficiency.

He presented in detail the case of lithium extraction and the new technologies available for sustainable extraction through direct lithium extraction (DLE), including its implications, practical examples, and development recommendations. The title of the presentation was “Technologies for Sustainable Lithium Extraction in Salt Flats: The Lithium Triangle as a Pillar of the Energy Transition.”

Allan Campos (Centro Nacional de Alta Tecnología, Costa Rica) - He is an Electromechanical Engineer with a Master's degree in Business Administration, currently pursuing a Ph.D. in Business Sciences with a focus on Circular Bioeconomy. He has collaborated as a researcher and leader in numerous national and international projects over the past 30 years. He worked for 7 years as a technology analyst at the Presidential Office of the Government of Costa Rica. He has been a Physics and Mechanics professor at several universities in Costa Rica for 24 years. Since 2011, he has been the Director of the Environmental Management Area at CENAT/CONARE in Costa Rica, and for 23 years he has managed national and international projects and events related to technology, innovation, and outreach within this institution.

He gave a presentation on circular bioeconomy and how it can serve as a pathway toward a sustainable and environmentally friendly energy transition.

Main conclusions

This panel aimed to present examples of possible solutions to the environmental challenges posed by the energy transition toward a model based on renewable sources. They were only that: examples. There are a lot of other successful initiatives in Latin American and European countries in the same way (for instance, a participant assisting the virtual thematic event presented the experience developed in Cuba related to the conservation of local plant genetic resources, solid waste processing, and biodiesel production).

While the positive environmental impact of transitioning to renewable energy is undeniable, there are challenges within the energy sector that must be addressed to mitigate the negative environmental effects that this transition can also generate. So that they do not end up offsetting the positives and causing the energy transition to lose its sustainability. If we truly want an authentic energy transition, this must be sustainable from social, environmental, and cultural perspectives.

Three key takeaways emerged:

- First, not only is it important what is being researched (for example, new technologies and innovations contributing to the energy transition), but also in who is doing it, how, and why. Participatory practices, co-generation of knowledge, and transformative solutions—such as the Solar Eco-Parking at the National University of the Austral Chaco in Argentina presented by Edgardo Chapur—are excellent examples of this approach.
- Second, a sustainable energy transition from an environmental perspective involves more than just changing the energy matrix; this requires doing so in a way that respects ecosystems and minimizes negative impacts. For instance, Energytran project perspective shows that the energy transition must be sustainable or it won't be a true transition. Álvaro Videla presented an example of how to address the effects of lithium mining on water resources and soil—lithium being a key mineral for electricity storage.
- Finally, Allan Campos shared how the productive system through circular bioeconomy can contribute to an environmentally sustainable energy transition. The use of agricultural, forestry, and urban waste as energy raw materials offers a real alternative to the intensive land use by monocultures for biomass energy production. This approach can also support rural development and green employment in the region and incorporate ancestral knowledge and skills.

4.5. Panel 4: Policies and regulations for the green energy transition

This panel examined current policies and regulatory frameworks supporting green and sustainable energy transitions, exploring their potential to foster socioeconomic and environmental development. Discussions addressed the impact of these frameworks not only on businesses and urban areas but also on rural and remote communities, adopting a comprehensive perspective that encompassed experiences and challenges from Latin America, Europe, and North America.

Moderator

Allan Campos Gallo (Centro Nacional de Alta Tecnología, Costa Rica) - He is an Electromechanical Engineer with a Master's degree in Business Administration, currently pursuing a Ph.D. in Business Sciences with a focus on Circular Bioeconomy. He has collaborated as a researcher and leader in numerous national and international projects over the past 30 years. He worked for 7 years as a technology analyst at the Presidential Office of the Government of Costa Rica. He has been a Physics and Mechanics professor at several universities in Costa Rica for 24 years. Since 2011, he has been the Director of the Environmental Management Area at CENAT/CONARE in Costa Rica, and for 23 years he has managed national and international projects and events related to technology, innovation, and outreach within this institution.

Panellists

Natalia Andrea Restrepo Velez (Comisión para la Cooperación Ambiental) - Natalia Restrepo is a Project Leader in the Environmental Quality Unit at the Commission for Environmental Cooperation (CEC). She currently supports the development and implementation of cooperative projects among Canada, the United States, and Mexico on issues related to climate change, the reduction of short-lived climate pollutants, and renewable energy in North America. She has over 10 years of experience working on projects with international organizations, governments, universities, and communities aimed at improving environmental conditions across the Americas. Natalia holds a degree in Process Engineering from EAFIT University (Colombia) and a Master's in Environmental Engineering from the University of Stuttgart (Germany).

Elena López Gunn (Real Instituto Elcano, España) - Elena López Gunn is a senior non-resident research fellow at the Elcano Royal Institute, founder and director of ICATALIST, and a leading expert in sustainability and climate change adaptation. She is a Lead Author for the IPCC Working Group II, a member of the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change, and contributes to UNESCO's Future of Water initiative, which works to strengthen science-policy connections for achieving SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation).

With a career spanning academia, international organizations, and public-private collaboration, Elena has worked extensively on water governance and collective action for sustainable resource management. She has served as an associate professor at IE Business School and a visiting scholar at water@leeds and the London School of Economics. Her collaborations include projects with UNESCO, FAO, UNDP, the European Commission, and NGOs such as Transparency International and The Nature Conservancy. She holds a PhD from King's College London and master's degrees from the University of Cambridge and the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos in Madrid.

Rodrigo Rojas Morales (Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica) - Rodrigo is a specialist in energy and the environment and has been working at the Costa Rican Institute of Electricity (ICE) for over 20 years. He currently leads the innovation working group, coordinates the Energy Foresight Observatory, and is a member of the expert team responsible for developing the portfolio of non-conventional renewable energies. In recent years, he has coordinated Costa Rica's roadmap for ocean energy and was the main organizer of PAMEC-2020 in Costa Rica. He is also a professor in the Department of Ecology at the National University of Costa Rica, where he supervises theses on topics related to energy and the environment.

Main conclusions

This panel exceeded expectations by featuring the participation of a North American expert in clean energy transition, a representative from the Commission for Environmental Cooperation (CEC), who collaborates closely with Indigenous communities across Canada, the United States, and Mexico.

This valuable contribution enabled a comparative analysis between the regulatory frameworks of North America, Europe, and Costa Rica, providing a broader understanding of regional approaches to sustainable energy development.

A key takeaway from the discussion was that, while the advancement of clean energy is essential for the long-term sustainability of humanity, it must be guided by policies and regulations that ensure the responsible use and preservation of natural resources, preventing their overexploitation. The CEC's bioeconomy strategy was highlighted as an exemplary initiative, integrating ancestral knowledge of clean and sustainable energy practices, an approach that holds strong potential for replication across the Americas and Europe.

In the European context, the EU has implemented robust regulations aimed at promoting sustainability and enhancing climate change adaptation. Meanwhile, Costa Rica stands out for its significant potential to generate clean energy; however, strategic actions are required to guarantee that this development remains environmentally sound and culturally respectful, particularly toward the traditions of the country's Indigenous peoples.

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ANNEXE: RESULTS OF THE VIRTUAL THEMATIC EVENTS SURVEYS

Results of the virtual thematic events' surveys

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VIRTUAL THEMATIC EVENT: RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES COOPERATION FOR ENERGY TRANSITION BETWEEN EUROPEAN AND LATIN AMERICAN AND THE CARIBBEAN

1. Panel 1: Knowledge Exchange in Scientific Cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 1: "How satisfied are you with Panel 1 'Knowledge Exchange in the Scientific Cooperation between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean?'". Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 90% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 1.
- 4% were neutral.
- The remaining percentage (6%) is divided between dissatisfied, very dissatisfied, and those who were unable to attend or do not recall.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 1 on knowledge exchange in scientific cooperation to be positive and useful.

2. Panel 2: Challenges and Opportunities in the Energy Sector

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 2: "How satisfied are you with Panel 2 "Challenges and Opportunities in the Energy Sector"?". Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 92% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 2.
- 2% were neutral.
- The remaining percentage (6%) is divided between dissatisfied, very dissatisfied, and those who were unable to attend or do not recall.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 2 to be positive and useful.

3. Panel 3: Environmental and Social Impact of the Energy Transition

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 3: How satisfied are you with Panel 3 "Environmental and Social Impact of Energy Transition"? Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 87% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 1.
- 4% were neutral.
- The remaining percentage (9%) is divided between dissatisfied, very dissatisfied, and those who were unable to attend or do not recall.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 3 on Environmental and Social Impact of Energy Transition.

4. Panel 4: Emerging Technologies for Energy Sustainability

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 1: How satisfied are you with the synthesis and conclusions of Panel 4 “Technologies for Energy Sustainability”? Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 88% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 1.
- 2% were neutral.
- The remaining percentage (10%) is divided between dissatisfied, very dissatisfied, and those who were unable to attend or do not recall.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 4 Technologies for Energy Sustainability to be positive and useful.

5. Panel 5: Applications of Solar Thermal Energy

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 5: How satisfied are you with the synthesis and conclusions of Panel 5 "Applications of Solar Thermal Energy"? Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 92% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 1.
- 2% were neutral.
- The remaining percentage (6%) is divided between dissatisfied, very dissatisfied, and those who were unable to attend or do not recall.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 5 on Applications of Solar Thermal Energy to be positive and useful.

6. General Satisfaction of the Virtual Thematic Event

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with the event: "Were topics discussed in the Virtual Thematic Event useful to identify critical issues related to technology for the energy transition?" Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 92% of respondents were useful or very useful.
- 8% were regular.

Also included “Please, assess how this Virtual Thematic Event addresses the exchange of knowledge between European and Latin-American countries on technology in energy transition?” Out of a total of 52 responses:

- 96% of respondents were well and very well.
- 2% were neutral.
- 2% were poorly

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered the event to be positive and useful.

VIRTUAL THEMATIC EVENT: SOCIAL IMPACT OF ENERGY TRANSITION

PANEL 1: SOCIAL DIMENSION OF ENERGY TRANSITION

Very satisfied	3
Satisfied	0
Neutral	0
Unsatisfied	0
Very unsatisfied	0
I don't know, I couldn't participate	2

PANEL 2: TERRITORIAL JUSTICE AND ENERGY TRANSITION

Very satisfied	3
Satisfied	0
Neutral	0
Unsatisfied	0
Very unsatisfied	0
I don't know, I couldn't participate	2

PANEL 3: GENDER EQUALITY AND ENERGY TRANSITION

Very satisfied	5
Satisfied	0
Neutral	0
Unsatisfied	0
Very unsatisfied	0
I don't know, I couldn't participate	0

PANEL 4: INDUSTRIAL POLICY AND ENERGY TRANSITION

● Very satisfied	4
● Satisfied	0
● Neutral	0
● Unsatisfied	0
● Very unsatisfied	0
● I don't know, I couldn't participate	1

PANEL 5: PUBLIC POLICY AND ENERGY TRANSITION

● Very satisfied	4
● Satisfied	0
● Neutral	0
● Unsatisfied	0
● Very unsatisfied	0
● I don't know, I couldn't participate	1

PANEL 6: OPEN SCIENCE AND ENERGY TRANSITION

Were topics discussed in the Virtual Thematic Event useful to identify critical issues related to social impact of the energy transition?

Please, assess how this Virtual Thematic Event addresses the exchange of knowledge between European and Latin-American countries on social impact of the energy transition?

VIRTUAL THEMATIC EVENT: TOWARDS AN ENVIRONMENTALLY SUSTAINABLE ENERGY TRANSITION

Panel 1: Challenges of a sustainable energy transition

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 1: "How satisfied are you with Panel 1?". Out of a total of 25 responses:

- 92% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 1.
- 8% were neutral.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 1 to be positive and useful.

4. How satisfied are you with Panel 1 "Challenges of a Sustainable Energy Transition"?

Panel 2: Environmental impact of renewable energies

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 1: "How satisfied are you with Panel 1?". Out of a total of 25 responses:

- 84% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 2.
- 16% were neutral.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 2 to be positive and useful.

5. How satisfied are you with Panel 2 "Environmental Impact of Renewable Energies"?

Panel 3: Solutions to environmental challenges in the energy transition

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 1: "How satisfied are you with Panel 1?". Out of a total of 25 responses:

- 76% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 3.
- 16% were neutral.
- 4% were unsatisfied.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 3 to be positive and useful.

6. How satisfied are you with Panel 3 "Solutions to Environmental Challenges in the Energy Transition"?

Panel 4: Policies and regulations for the green energy transition

The general event survey includes a specific question regarding attendees' satisfaction with Panel 1: "How satisfied are you with Panel 1?". Out of a total of 25 responses:

- 88% of respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with Panel 4.
- 8% were neutral.
- 4% were unsatisfied.

These results suggest that, overall, attendees of the thematic virtual event considered Panel 4 to be positive and useful.

7. How satisfied are you with Panel 4 "Policies and Regulations for the Green Energy Transition"?

Very satisfied	15
Satisfied	7
Neutral	2
Unsatisfied	1
Very unsatisfied	0
I don't know, I couldn't participate	0

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